

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Polymorphism in *Oryza malampuzhaensis*

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Studies on *O. malampuzhaensis* Krishn. et Chandn., a tetraploid wild rice from South India, are scanty because it is poorly represented in germplasm and herbarium collections. We compared recent collections of this taxon: Ac 42 from the National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources Regional Station, Trichur, India, and four accessions collected from natural habitats along the western Ghat, South India (Ac 51 from Parambikulam, Ac 55 from Nilambur, Ac 56 from Vellani, and Ac 57 from Peechi).

Tillers at the 3-leaf stage were separated from the perennial parent plant and grown in pots, with four replications. A minimum 5 tillers/plant were observed at appropriate stages of development (see table).

Accessions varied in all characters evaluated except chromosome number. Meiotic studies showed regular forma-

Variation in quantitative and qualitative characters of 5 accessions of tetraploid wild rice from South India.

Character	Mean					LSD (p=0.05)
	Ac 42	Ac 51	Ac 55	Ac 56	Ac 57	
Boot leaf length (cm)	27.5	25.3	20.1	23.3	21.0	2.28
Boot leaf width (cm)	2.0	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.5	0.09
Peduncle length (cm)	60.1	64.7	47.2	50.9	57.9	6.59
1st internode length (cm)	28.2	25.0	20.0	20.5	23.2	2.73
Culm length (cm)	127.7	115.0	73.1	80.9	88.5	10.21
Panicle length (cm)	21.8	19.7	17.8	21.4	18.7	1.93
Av length of primary branch (cm)	12.3	13.5	9.1	10.7	9.9	1.96
No. of primary branches/panicle	9.7	6.6	6.7	6.1	6.2	0.74
No. of spikelets/panicle	166.6	118.3	81.0	88.2	82.9	16.02
Ligule length (mm)	3.1	2.9	1.8	2.7	2.7	0.17
Spikelet length (mm)	6.1	5.6	4.9	5.8	5.4	0.16
Spikelet width (mm)	2.3	2.5	2.2	2.3	2.4	0.12
Spikelet length/width ratio	2.6	2.3	2.2	2.5	2.2	0.15
Spikelet thickness (mm)	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.4	0.05
Sterile glume length (mm)	1.2	1.5	1.0	1.5	1.3	0.12
Awn length (cm)	0.4	1.4	0.7	0.7	0.9	0.18
Chromosome number (n)	24	24	24	24	24	
Pollen sterility (%)	8.9	5.4	10.9	26.4	65.7	
Ligule fringing	Long, very dense	Short, sparse	Short, dense	Short, very sparse	Very long, moderately dense	
Stigma color	Very dark purple	Dark purple	White	Purple	Dark purple	
Blooming time	0730-1030 h	0800-1200 h	0800-1200 h	0800-1400 h	0730-1500 h	

tion of 24 bivalents at diakinesis. It is evident this taxon is polymorphic, with much wider distribution than was

hitherto known. Further studies are needed to elucidate its taxonomic status and evolutionary position. ■

Breeding methods

Identifying maintainers and restorers of CMS lines for hybrid rice breeding

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We crossed 40 rice cultivars as pollen parents with cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines V20 A, V97 A, Pankhari 203 A, IR46826 A, IR54752 A, and IR54753 A, to identify maintainers and restorers for varying agroclimate and

Table 1. Maintainers and restorers in the CMS lines of rice.

Cultivar	Classification ^a					
	V20 A	V97 A	Pankhari 203 A	IR46826 A	IR54752 A	IR54753 A
Bala	PR	M	PR	PR	R	R
Kiran	PR	PR	PR	PR	R	PR
Kanchan	PR	R	PM	PR	PM	PM
Browngora	PM	R	PR	PR	PR	PR
Birsa Dhan 101	PM	PR	PM	PR	PR	PR
Birsa Dhan 202	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM
Basmati 370	R	PR	PM	PM		PM
Rajendra Dhan 202	R	PR	PM	R	R	PR
Sita	PR	PR	PM	PM	PR	PM
BR8	PM	PM	PR	R	M	PR
BR9	PM	M	PR	PR	PR	PM
RAU4045-10	M	M			PM	PR
Akashi	M	PR		R		PR
Rasi	PR	PR	PR	PR	PR	M
Ratna	PR	R	PM	R	R	PR
Mahsuri	PM	R	PM	PR	PR	PR

continued next page.